

Investigating the Impact of Temperature and Humidity on SINR Variations in LTE Networks: A Field Study

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ABSTRACT:

Network planning and optimization in the telecommunications industry face significant challenges due to fluctuating Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) conditions, which can lead to inaccuracies in drive test reports and complicate efforts to enhance network performance. Despite the recognized importance of SINR in assessing network quality, few studies have focused on how atmospheric conditions, such as temperature and humidity, directly influence SINR variation in real-world LTE networks. This research aims to fill this gap by investigating the impact of temperature and humidity on SINR in LTE networks in Sri Lanka. Through real-time field testing and data collection over a 24-hour period, we analyze the relationship between environmental factors and SINR variation using statistical models. The findings indicate that both temperature and humidity significantly affect SINR, with the exponential model offering the best fit for SINR variation. These results highlight the importance of considering atmospheric conditions in network optimization strategies, providing valuable insights for improving the reliability and efficiency of LTE networks in dynamic environments.

Keywords: Signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), LTE Network Performance, Temperature and Humidity Effects, Wireless Communication Optimization.

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INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication has become an integral part of modern life, seamlessly connecting people, devices, and systems globally. Over the years, it has evolved from basic voice transmission to sophisticated data communication systems, revolutionizing how we interact, access information, and consume media. As the demand for high-quality wireless connectivity grows, understanding and addressing the factors influencing signal quality in wireless networks becomes crucial.

One effective method employed by telecommunications operators to meet these demands is drive testing [1]. This technique involves collecting real-time data by traversing a network's coverage area, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of network performance, signal quality, and coverage. By identifying key areas of improvement, drive testing provides valuable insights that help optimize wireless communication systems, ensuring they meet the ever-increasing expectations for reliability and efficiency [2,3].

Figure 1. Scope of Drive Testing

Figure 1 illustrates the scope of drive testing, highlighting its applications in assessing network coverage, signal quality, and performance, and its importance to key stakeholders. Given its critical role in network optimization, understanding the variables that impact signal quality during these tests is essential [3,4].

This research aims to investigate how environmental factors, specifically temperature and humidity, impact the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR). SINR is a critical metric in network optimization reports, used to estimate downlink coverage and measure the quality of the downlink between the user equipment (UE) and its serving cell for network planning and optimization purposes [5].

Favourable SINR conditions lead to more bits per modulation symbol being transmitted, achieving higher throughput, more reliable connections, and overall improved network performance, thus

enhancing user experiences. Conversely, unfavourable SINR conditions result in fewer bits per symbol being transmitted, leading to lower throughput, increased interference and noise, frequent connection drops, and degraded performance, negatively impacting user experience and network efficiency. Understanding how temperature and humidity affect SINR can provide valuable insights for optimizing network performance under varying environmental conditions [6].

This study seeks to elucidate the correlation between atmospheric conditions and SINR, thereby informing strategies for network optimization under varying environmental conditions. Figure 2 illustrates the iterative process of radio network optimization, focusing on improving network reliability and efficiency by adjusting to varying SINR conditions [3].

Figure 2. Radio Network Optimization Procedure

However, in real-world scenarios, it is not always possible to conduct tests at the same time or under identical conditions. Therefore, environmental factors must be considered when determining the optimal SINR levels for a given location.

Figure 3. Drive Test Conducted at Sri Lanka, Central Province, Kandy District, Ethgala (7.136103, 80.572148). The Tests were Performed during Two Time Periods: Daytime Test (L) from 1:00 PM to 4:00 PM, and Nighttime Test (R) from 2:00 AM to 5:00 AM.

Figure 3 illustrates the variation in SINR observed during both daytime and nighttime at the same geographical location under varying atmospheric conditions in the Central Province of Sri Lanka. These variations suggest a potential correlation between environmental factors and SINR fluctuations. While further investigation is needed to establish direct causation, this study aims to quantify the extent to which these environmental factors influence SINR fluctuations. Understanding this impact is essential for refining network optimization strategies and ensuring consistent and high-quality wireless network performance across diverse conditions.

RELATED WORK

Wireless communication systems are highly sensitive to environmental factors that impact the Signal to Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR), a key determinant of network performance. Extensive research has been conducted to examine how different environmental conditions, models, and system parameters influence SINR in wireless networks. This section provides an overview of related works that explore the role of environmental factors and models in SINR prediction and optimization.

SINR in Wireless Networks: Definition and Importance

The SINR measures the ratio of the power received from the serving cell to the sum power of the interfering ones and the thermal noise, providing a direct measure of signal quality relative to interference and noise, which allows network engineers to evaluate the stability and reliability of the wireless link [2].

$$SINR = \frac{P_S}{P_N + P_I} \quad (1)$$

Where: P_S - Signal power received from the desired source, P_N - Power of the noise present in the system, including thermal noise, P_I - Power of the interference from other signals within the channel.

This equation provides a direct measure of the quality of the signal relative to the interference and noise, allowing network engineers to evaluate the stability and reliability of the wireless link. SINR serves as a fundamental parameter for optimizing performance in LTE networks, where a higher SINR results in better signal reception, reducing transmission errors and enhancing overall user experience [2,8].

Environmental Factors Affecting SINR

Environmental conditions, particularly humidity and temperature, significantly influence SINR in wireless networks. Elevated humidity levels in the atmosphere cause increased signal attenuation, as water vapor absorbs part of the electromagnetic wave's energy. This process weakens signal strength and heightens interference [10]. Similarly, temperature variations influence network performance, as higher temperatures can contribute to increased thermal noise power, potentially reducing the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) and affecting the efficiency of wireless communication systems [11].

One study by Luomala et al. [12] highlights the crucial role of temperature and humidity in signal strength variations. Their findings suggest that temperature generally has a negative, linear effect on signal strength, with higher temperatures correlating with weaker signals. They also observed that relative humidity can influence signal strength, especially when temperatures are below freezing. This aligns with the observations of Luomala et al. [12], where changes in weather conditions, particularly temperature and humidity, were shown to cause temporal and spatial fluctuations in radio signal strength, thereby affecting the performance of WSNs. In particular, their study revealed that temperature was the most significant factor in signal strength variation, with high relative humidity having some effect, but only under specific conditions.

A study on the impact of precipitation on distance estimation in a 1.8 GHz GSM network found that weather conditions, such as rain and wind, significantly degrade accuracy in distance estimation.

The conventional rain attenuation model underestimated these effects, and the results emphasized the need to consider weather when estimating distance based on received signal strength (RSS), even in low-frequency GSM networks [13].

Ekah et al.[15] demonstrated how humidity, temperature, wind speed, and rainfall influence the Call Setup Success Rate (CSSR) in wireless networks. The study found that these atmospheric variables affect SINR irregularly, showing a correlation between tropospheric changes and network performance.

Choudhary et al. [16] provided further insights into the effects of temperature, air quality index, and relative humidity on mobile signal strength. Their study demonstrated that increased relative humidity (from 25% to 75%) resulted in reduced signal strength across 2G, 3G, and 4G networks, thereby affecting SINR. Additionally, rising temperatures caused a marginal decrease in signal strength due to the increased resistivity of the transmission medium.

Mathematical Model for SINR Prediction

The SINR (Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio) distribution is closely related to the network geometry, specifically the spatial interactions between points in the network. It serves as a critical evaluation metric for selecting the most suitable Point Process (PP) model to match empirical data.

Assume that a reference user y is located at the origin of a point pattern Φ and is connected to the nearest base station (BS) $x_0 \in \Phi$. The downlink SINR can be mathematically expressed as:

$$SINR(x_0; y) = \frac{P_{tx} h_{x_0} \ell(\|x_0\|)}{\sigma^2 + \sum_{x_i \in \Phi \setminus \{x_0\}} P_{tx} h_{x_i} \ell(\|x_i\|)} \quad (2)$$

Where: P_{tx} - Transmit power of the base station (BS), h_x - random variable that captures multi-path fading and/or shadowing between user y and BS x , $\ell(\| \cdot \|)$ - Path loss function, σ^2 - Noise power variance.

The numerator of the SINR equation quantifies the received signal power from the serving base station x_0 , while the denominator includes the combined impact of noise and interference power from all other base stations x_i in the network [14].

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Data Collection and Methodology

To evaluate the influence of atmospheric conditions on SINR, data collection was performed over a continuous 24-hour period at a designated location. The location was chosen to balance accessibility and environmental relevance, situated 510 meters away from the nearest cell tower (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Data Collection Site Layout and Distance to the Cell Tower

The SINR measurements were recorded using TEMS Investigation Software, a widely used tool in the field of wireless communication for network performance analysis.

The selected site provided a stable environment, ideal for assessing the effects of atmospheric factors on signal quality. Located in a suburban area, the test location offered a direct line of sight to the nearest cell tower, ensuring minimal obstruction and accurate signal measurement (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Elevation Profile and Spatial Layout between the Cell Tower (6°51'6.66"N, 80°5'16.51"E) and the Test Location (6°51'14.44"N, 80°5'27.67"E), Situated within the Western Province, Colombo District, SLTC Research University Premises

Note: The elevation profile highlights the topographical changes along the path. The image was captured using Google Earth, illustrating the relationship between the test location and the cell tower for the test.

Alongside SINR measurements, atmospheric data such as temperature and humidity were recorded. This facilitated a precise correlation between SINR variations and real-time environmental conditions.

To ensure robust analysis, SINR and environmental parameters were logged at hourly intervals. Data collection for each hour involved a 5-minute sampling period, during which SINR values were recorded. The median SINR value for each hour was then calculated to capture diurnal variations in atmospheric conditions while maintaining a balance between data granularity and manageability.

This methodology ensures that the collected data accurately represents real-world conditions, with a primary focus on the influence of temperature and humidity. Although efforts were made to minimize the impact of other variables through consistent location and measurement techniques, it is acknowledged that factors such as signal interference, network configurations, and environmental obstructions may also contribute to SINR fluctuations. The study aims to assess the relationship between atmospheric factors and SINR, while recognizing and considering these potential limitations.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Hourly measurements were taken to monitor variations in SINR. Four statistical measures—mean, minimum, maximum, and median—were calculated for each hour, resulting in multiple perspectives on SINR fluctuations over time. These variations are visually represented in Figure 6, which shows distinct lines for each statistical measure. The median SINR value will be used in future work as it provides a more robust and representative measure, being less sensitive to outliers and better reflecting typical network conditions.

Figure 6. SINR Statistics per Hour (Mean, Min, Max, Median)

The Impact of Temperature and Humidity on SINR

Figure 7. Median SINR, Temperature and Humidity Variation over Time

The analysis reveals that temperature and humidity have a significant impact on SINR. Hourly variations in both environmental factors were recorded alongside SINR values, and their influence was thoroughly analyzed. As shown in Figure 7, temperature and humidity variations over the 24-hour period demonstrate notable correlations with SINR fluctuations.

Humidity was found to have a dual effect on SINR. Higher humidity levels typically result in increased signal attenuation, leading to a decrease in received signal power, which directly reduces SINR. Humidity can also introduce interference and scattering, further degrading signal quality [17]. However, my findings showed that in some instances, particularly during periods of higher humidity coupled with lower temperatures, SINR values were higher. This phenomenon can be attributed to the reduction in power from overshooting cells under high humidity conditions, which helped alleviate interference and led to improved SINR.

This dual effect of humidity highlights its complex role in network performance. On the one hand, it increases signal attenuation and scattering, which negatively impacts SINR [12,17]. On the other hand, in certain conditions, such as when temperature drops, the reduced interference from overshooting cells can have a positive effect on SINR. These findings suggest that the impact of humidity on SINR is not always straightforward and depends on other contributing factors such as temperature [12].

Similarly, temperature has a direct relationship with SINR. As the temperature rises, thermal noise increases, leading to greater interference and a reduction in signal quality. This is particularly evident during warmer periods, where SINR tends to drop[12]. Conversely, lower temperatures, especially at night, provided more favorable conditions for signal propagation, resulting in improved SINR.

The interplay between temperature and humidity is evident throughout the monitoring period. For instance, during the early morning hours when the temperature was low and humidity was high, SINR values were more stable. In contrast, during peak daytime hours when the temperature was high and humidity was low, SINR experienced more fluctuations due to the combined effects of thermal noise and interference [17].

While prior research suggests that higher humidity generally leads to lower SINR due to increased signal attenuation and interference [12], my findings reveal that higher humidity can sometimes improve SINR when accompanied by lower temperatures and reduced cell power. This highlights the need to consider both the positive and negative effects of humidity when assessing its impact on network performance.

Figure 8. Median SINR Variation over Time with Max/Min Time Frames

Based on Figure 8, a clear pattern in SINR values is observed over a 24-hour period. The highest SINR values occur between 1:00 and 4:00, while the lowest values are seen between 14:00 and 16:00. This pattern has significant implications for network optimization. By considering these factors in network optimization, engineers can adjust parameters like power levels, antenna configurations, or channel allocations to mitigate the effects on SINR.

Field test engineers can also leverage this pattern to organize drive tests during periods of higher or lower SINR, depending on their specific objectives. For example, drive tests during low SINR periods may highlight areas needing optimization, while tests during higher SINR periods could help evaluate network stability under favourable conditions.

However, one of the key challenges network engineers often face is the difficulty in determining whether observed SINR levels are accurate or typical for a specific location. Without understanding the expected SINR patterns, inaccurate reports can lead to sub-optimal network adjustments and, ultimately, poor network performance. Therefore, identifying reliable SINR patterns is crucial for more accurate reporting and effective network optimization strategies.

Figure 9. Median SINR, Temperature and Humidity Variation over Time with Max/Min Time Frames

In addition to SINR variations, environmental factors such as temperature and humidity also influence SINR performance, as shown in Figure 9. The figure highlights two critical periods:

- **Low Temperature & High Humidity (Hours 0-6):** This period coincides with the highest SINR values, indicating that cooler temperatures and higher humidity levels may help maintain stronger signal quality.
- **High-Temperature & Low Humidity (Hours 12-18):** During this time, SINR values drop significantly, likely due to increased noise and interference caused by higher temperatures and lower humidity.

These findings suggest that temperature and humidity should also be factored into network planning and optimization strategies, especially in regions with significant climate variability.

Modeling SINR-Temperature/Humidity Relationship

To analyze the impact of temperature and humidity on SINR variation, multiple statistical models were employed: linear, polynomial, logarithmic, exponential, and power law models. These models were used to explore how SINR fluctuates with temperature and humidity individually, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how each factor influences network performance.

The SINR values were plotted against temperature using the five different statistical models to observe how each model captures the relationship between temperature and SINR. Figure 10 illustrates these models and their respective fits, showing how SINR behaves under varying temperature conditions.

Figure 10. SINR Variation with Temperature across Different Models

Table 1 provides the equations and corresponding coefficient values for the statistical models used to analyze SINR variation with temperature. Each model aims to capture the relationship between SINR and temperature, offering insights into how SINR behaves under varying environmental conditions.

Table 1. Model Equations and Coefficients for SINR vs Temperature

Model	Equation	Coefficient Values
Linear Model	$f(x) = ax + b$	$a = -0.6593, b = 38.1165$
Polynomial Model	$f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$	$a = 0.1113, b = -7.5913, c = 121.2113$
Exponential Model	$f(x) = a \cdot \exp(bx) + c$	$a = 54.0799, b = -0.0731, c = 11.0806$
Logarithmic Model	$f(x) = a \cdot \log(x) + b$	$a = -13.6635, b = 65.2257$
Power Law Model	$f(x) = a \cdot x^b$	$a = 1620.3650, b = -2.8262$

To evaluate the goodness of fit for the regression models, the coefficient of determination, denoted as R^2 , is employed. Let y_i represent the observed values of the dependent variable (in this case, SINR), where $(i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$. The mean \bar{y} of the observed values, denoted as \bar{y} , is calculated as follows:

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \quad (3)$$

where n is the total number of observations.

The total variability in the observed data can be quantified using the *Total Sum of Squares* (SS_{tot}), which measures the squared differences between each observed value y_i and the mean \bar{y} :

$$SS_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2 \quad (4)$$

To assess how well the model predicts the observed values, we utilize the *Predicted Values* \hat{y}_i , which are derived from the regression model. The difference between the observed values y_i and the predicted values \hat{y}_i is captured by the *Residual Sum of Squares* (SS_{res}):

$$SS_{res} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

The explained variability, or how much of the total variability is accounted for by the model, is measured by the *Explained Sum of Squares* (SS_{exp}):

$$SS_{exp} = \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2 \quad (6)$$

The R^2 value is then calculated as the ratio of the explained variability to the total variability:

$$R^2 = \frac{SS_{exp}}{SS_{tot}} = 1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{tot}} \quad (7)$$

Here, R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, where $R^2 = 1$ indicates that the model perfectly explains the observed data, and $R^2 = 0$ means that the model does not explain any of the variability. In practice, higher values of R^2 indicate a better fit between the model and the data [21,23].

In this research, various regression models were compared based on their R^2 values to identify the model that best fits the data. The R^2 value quantifies the proportion of variance in the dependent variable, SINR, that can be explained by the independent variable, temperature. The results of the R^2 values for the different models are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Values for Different Statistical Models

Model	Value
Linear Model	0.2657
Polynomial Model	0.3457
Exponential Model	0.3866
Logarithmic Model	0.2782
Power Law Model	0.2901

The R^2 values indicate how well each model explains the variability in SINR. For instance, the linear model, with an R^2 value of 0.2657, suggests that approximately 26.57% of the variance in SINR can be attributed to temperature. In contrast, the exponential model exhibits a higher R^2 value of 0.3866, indicating that 38.66% of the variance in SINR is explained by temperature under this model. This makes the exponential model the most suitable for capturing the relationship between temperature and SINR in the scenario, as it accounts for a larger portion of the variation compared to the other models.

It is crucial to note that while the R^2 value provides insight into the strength of the relationship between temperature and SINR, it does not imply causality. The correlation simply reflects the degree to which the two variables are related, acknowledging that other factors may also influence SINR. As stated by Field (2013) [19], a higher R^2 value indicates a stronger relationship, but the presence of unexplained variance emphasizes that further investigation may be required to fully understand the dynamics between these variables.

The SINR values were also plotted against humidity using the five statistical models to observe how each model captures the relationship between humidity and SINR. Figure 11 illustrates these models and their respective fits, showing how SINR varies with changes in humidity.

Figure 11. SINR Variation with Humidity across Different Models

Table III provides the equations and coefficient values for the models used to analyze SINR variation with humidity.

Table 3. Model Equations and Coefficients for SINR vs Humidity

Model	Equation	Coefficient Values
Linear Model	$f(x) = ax + b$	$a = -0.3516, b = 46.7254$
Polynomial Model	$f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$	$a = -0.0015, b = 0.5172, c = 24.1246$
Exponential Model	$f(x) = a \cdot \exp(bx) + c$	$a = 25.6731, b = -0.0152, c = 14.2390$
Logarithmic Model	$f(x) = a \cdot \log(x) + b$	$a = -4.7685, b = 49.2537$
Power Law Model	$f(x) = a \cdot x^b$	$a = 98.4617, b = -0.7216$

Table 4 summarizes the R^2 values for the models analyzing the relationship between SINR and humidity.

Table 4. Values for Different Models of SINR vs Humidity

Model	Value
Linear Model	0.2073
Polynomial Model	0.2735
Exponential Model	0.3412
Logarithmic Model	0.1984
Power Law Model	0.2187

The R^2 values highlight the performance of each model in explaining the variance in SINR based on humidity. The exponential model again provides the highest R^2 value at 0.3412, indicating that 34.12% of the variance in SINR can be explained by humidity under this model. This suggests that, as with temperature, the exponential model captures the relationship between SINR and humidity better than the other models. However, as emphasized earlier, while the R^2 value demonstrates the strength of the relationship, it does not imply causality. The results simply suggest a relationship between SINR and humidity, but other environmental factors may also contribute to variations in SINR.

Multivariate Regression Analysis

In this section, a multivariate regression analysis is used to examine how temperature and humidity jointly influence the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR). Unlike univariate models, which consider only one independent variable at a time, this approach accounts for multiple variables simultaneously, making it more comprehensive [20,22].

a. R-squared (R^2)

The R^2 value, also known as the coefficient of determination, quantifies the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables in the model [21,23].

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{\sum(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2} \quad (8)$$

Where: Y_i is the observed value of SINR, \hat{Y}_i is the predicted value of SINR from the regression model, \bar{Y} is the mean of the observed values.

b. Adjusted R-squared (R_{adj}^2)

The adjusted R^2 accounts for the number of predictors in the model, penalizing unnecessary predictors. It provides a more accurate measure of model fit, especially when comparing models with different numbers of predictors, and can decrease if irrelevant predictors are added [21,24].

$$R_{adj}^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{(1-R^2)(n-1)}{n-p-1} \right) \quad (9)$$

Where: n is the number of data points, p is the number of predictors (in this case, 2: temperature and humidity).

c. F-statistic and Prob (F-statistic)}

The F-statistic assesses the overall significance of the model, testing if at least one predictor has a significant relationship with the dependent variable. A low p-value indicates that the model is statistically significant and at least one predictor is important in explaining the variability of the dependent variable [21].

$$F = \frac{SSR/p}{SSE / (n - p - 1)} \quad (10)$$

Where: SSR is the sum of squares due to regression (explained variance), SSE is the sum of squares due to error (unexplained variance), p is the number of predictors, n is the number of observations.

d. AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) and BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion)

AIC and BIC are model selection criteria that balance fit with complexity, penalizing excessive predictors to avoid overfitting. Lower AIC or BIC values indicate better models. AIC is more lenient toward complexity, while BIC applies a stricter penalty, especially with larger sample sizes. These criteria are useful for comparing models [21].

$$AIC = n \cdot \log \left(\frac{SSE}{n} \right) + 2p \quad (11)$$

$$BIC = n \cdot \log \left(\frac{SSE}{n} \right) + p \cdot \log(n) \quad (12)$$

Multivariate Linear Regression Analysis

Linear regression models are commonly employed for investigating relationships between variables due to their simplicity and interpretability. In this analysis, a multivariate linear regression model was

applied to assess the effect of temperature (T) and humidity (H) on SINR[25]. The linear model can be expressed as:

$$\widehat{SINR} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot T + \beta_2 \cdot H + \epsilon \quad (13)$$

Where: \widehat{SINR} - the dependent variable in decibels, β_0 - Intercept, the baseline SINR when T and H are zero, β_1 - Coefficient for temperature T, indicating SINR change per unit temperature increase, β_2 - Coefficient for humidity H, indicating SINR change per unit humidity increase, T - Temperature, H - Humidity, ϵ - Error term, accounting for unexplained SINR variability.

This equation models SINR as a function of temperature and humidity, serving as a regression framework rather than a physical definition.

Table 5. Multivariate Linear Regression Model Summary

Metric	Value
R-squared (R ²)	0.270
Adjusted R-squared	0.200
F-statistic	3.879
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0368
AIC	116.9
BIC	120.5

The linear regression model showed an R² value of 0.270, indicating a modest fit, suggesting that other unexamined factors may contribute to the observed SINR variability. The p-values for both temperature and humidity were above the 0.05 threshold, indicating that these variables, in isolation, may not significantly affect SINR. Despite these limitations, the linear model provides a simple and interpretable baseline for understanding the potential impact of environmental factors on SINR.

Multivariate Exponential Regression Analysis

Given that linear models may not adequately capture non-linear relationships in wireless signal propagation, we next employed a multivariate exponential regression model to account for potential non-linearities. The model was transformed using a logarithmic scale to better reflect the multiplicative nature of SINR [26]:

$$\widehat{SINR} = e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot T + \beta_2 \cdot H} + \epsilon \quad (14)$$

Where the variables are defined as above, with the exponential term capturing the non-linear dependency of SINR on temperature and humidity. The exponential model yielded an improved R² of 0.275, which, while still modest, represents a slight improvement over the linear model. This suggests that SINR is more appropriately modeled using a non-linear relationship with temperature and humidity, reflecting the complex nature of wireless signal behavior in varying atmospheric conditions.

Table 6. Multivariate Exponential Regression Model Summary

Metric	Value
R-squared (R ²)	0.275
Adjusted R-squared	0.206
F-statistic	3.977
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0343
AIC	-22.00
BIC	-18.46

Multivariate Exponential Regression Analysis with Interaction Variable

To further explore the potential interactions between temperature and humidity, an interaction term was incorporated into the exponential regression model. This model allows for a more nuanced understanding of how the combined variations in temperature and humidity affect SINR, as these variables may not act independently in real-world conditions[27]. The model is expressed as:

$$\widehat{SINR} = e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1.T + \beta_2.H + \beta_3.(T.H)} + \epsilon \quad (15)$$

Where: β_3 - Coefficient for the interaction term $T.H$, quantifies the combined effect of temperature and humidity on SINR.

Table 7. Multivariate Exponential Regression Model with Interaction Term Summary

Metric	Value
R-squared ()	0.464
Adjusted R-squared	0.384
F-statistic	5.782
Prob (F-statistic)	0.00514
AIC	-27.28
BIC	-22.57

The inclusion of the interaction term resulted in the highest R^2 value of 0.464, a notable improvement over both the linear and exponential models. This suggests that the interaction between temperature and humidity plays a significant role in determining SINR. The model's higher explanatory power indicates that environmental factors may not only affect SINR independently but also through their combined effect. Despite this, the p-values for the individual coefficients, including the interaction term, were still above 0.05, indicating that further refinement of the model or more precise data may be required to achieve statistical significance.

The inclusion of the interaction term also led to a reduction in the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), further supporting the improved fit of the model. While the p-values suggest that temperature, humidity, and the interaction term may not yet show strong statistical significance, the model's increased R^2 indicates that it provides a more accurate representation of SINR variability under fluctuating environmental conditions.

CONCLUSION

This study offers critical insights into the impact of atmospheric variables—temperature and humidity—on Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) within LTE networks. Through real-time data analysis spanning a 24-hour period, significant SINR fluctuations were observed, underscoring the role of environmental conditions in shaping network performance. Among the evaluated regression frameworks, the multivariate exponential model demonstrated superior capability in capturing the non-linear relationship between SINR and environmental factors, positioning it as a robust tool for predictive modeling and network optimization.

The findings emphasize the need for network planners to integrate environmental variability, particularly temperature and humidity, into SINR estimation and mitigation strategies. While this study focused on these two factors, SINR dynamics are inherently multifaceted, influenced by additional variables such as interference, physical obstructions, and network traffic. Addressing these complexities in future research will be essential for developing a holistic understanding of SINR behavior.

To advance this field, expanded data collection across diverse geographic regions and extended timeframes is recommended to better isolate environmental effects. Incorporating machine learning

techniques could further refine predictive accuracy and enable adaptive, real-time network adjustments. Such innovations hold promise for enhancing LTE reliability under dynamic atmospheric conditions while fostering energy-efficient and resilient wireless systems.

Ultimately, this research underscores the importance of environmental considerations in wireless communication performance and provides a foundation for optimizing current and next-generation networks through data-driven, interdisciplinary approaches.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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